

Glycosylium ions in superacid mimic the transition state of enzyme reactions

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I. General Information

Solvents: All anhydrous solvents were purchased from Acros and used as received.

Reagents: All commercially available reagents were used as purchased.

Chromatography: Flash chromatographies were carried out using Merck 9385 Kieselgel 60 silica gel under air atmosphere or using puriFlash® columns (30 µm) on a CombiFlash® apparatus from Teledyne. Thin layer chromatographies were carried out on Merck Kieselgel 60 F254 0.2 mm plates. Visualization was accomplished using ultraviolet light (254 nm) and followed by heating with a heat gun chemical staining with a solution of phosphomolybdic acid in EtOH (3g/100mL).

Data Collection: ¹H, ¹³C and ¹⁹F NMR spectra were recorded at 400 MHz for ¹H, 100 MHz for ¹³C and 376 MHz for ¹⁹F on a Bruker Advance 400 DPX spectrometer at 298 ± 3 K using CDCl₃ or CD₃OD as solvent or CD₃COCD₃ as external reference for *in situ* NMR. Chemical shifts (δ) are quoted in parts per million (ppm) relative to residual solvent (CHCl₃: δ_H = 7.26 ppm for ¹H and CDCl₃: δ_C = 77.16 ppm for ¹³C). Coupling constants (*J*) are quoted to the nearest 0.1 Hz. The following abbreviations are used to indicate the multiplicity of the signals: s = singlet; d = doublet; t = triplet; q = quartet; m = multiplet; br. = broad; and associated combinations, e.g. dd = doublet of doublets. H' attributions are used to indicate the protonation of hydroxyl group in superacid media. DEPT 135 and 2-dimensional experiments (COSY, HSQC, HMBC and NOESY) were used to support assignments when appropriated. High resolution mass spectra (HRMS) were recorded on a Bruker Q-TOF Impact HD apparatus using a positive electrospray (ESI) ionization source.

Superacid experiments: The authors draw the reader's attention to the dangerous features of superacidic chemistry. Handling of hydrogen fluoride and antimony pentafluoride must be done by experienced chemists with all the necessary safety arrangements in place. Experiments performed in superacid were carried out in a sealed Teflon® flask with a magnetic stirrer. No further precautions have to be taken to prevent reaction mixture from moisture.

II. Preparation of glycosyl donors

■ Methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1**

Methyl 2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1.1**

To a solution of the commercially available 3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl-D-glucal (3.0 g, 7.20 mmol) in anhydrous acetonitrile (30 mL) were added anhydrous MeOH (291 μ L, 7.20 mmol) and quickly ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) (79 mg, 0.14 mmol). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 36 h under inert atmosphere, the mixture was treated with diethyl ether (60 mL) and the mixture was washed with a saturated solution of NaHCO₃ (60 mL x3) and brine (60 mL x2). The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by flash chromatography column (SiO₂, petroleum ether/AcOEt 9:1) to afford the desired product **1.1** as a white solid (1.5 g, 48 % yield, α/β : 50/50).

R_f = 0.24 (EP/AcOEt 9:1); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 7.32-7.18 (m, 30H, H_{Ar}), 4.90 (dd, 1H, J = 2.1, 10.8 Hz, H_{1- β}), 4.86 (d, 1H, J = 2.7 Hz, H_{1- α}), 4.64 (m, 6H, CH₂Ph), 4.60 (d, 1H, J = 5.1 Hz, CH₂Ph), 4.57 (d, 1H, J = 12.8 Hz, CH₂Ph), 4.51 (dd, 3H, J = 7.4, 11.5 Hz, CH₂Ph), 4.36 (dd, 1H, J = 1.9, 9.7 Hz, H_{4- β}), 3.96 (m, 1H, H_{4- α}), 3.70 (m, 6H, H₅, H₆), 3.50 (s, 3H, H₇), 3.42 (m, 2H, H_{3- α/β}), 3.31 (s, 3H, H₇), 2.34 (ddd, 1H, J = 1.8, 5.0, 12.5 Hz, H_{2- α}), 2.28 (ddd, 1H, J = 1.1, 5.1, 12.9 Hz, H_{2- α}), 1.72 (ddd, 1H, J = 3.6, 11.6, 13.0 Hz, H_{2- β}), 1.63 (m, 1H, H_{2- β}); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm): 138.8 (1C, C_q), 138.7 (1C, C_q), 138.5 (1C, C_q), 138.4 (2C, C_q), 138.3 (1C, C_q), 128.6 – 127.6 (30C, CH_{Ar}), 100.9 (C_{1 β}), 98.6 (C_{1 α}), 79.5 (1C), 78.3 (2C), 75.3 (1C), 73.6 (1C), 71.6 (2C), 70.7 (1C), 69.4 (C₆), 69.0 (C₆), 56.8 (CH₂Ph), 54.7 (CH₂Ph), 36.7 (C₂), 35.5 (C₂).

Analytical data in agreement with literature [1].

Methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1**

To a solution of methyl 2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1.1** (1.5 g, 3.34 mmol) in anhydrous MeOH (150 mL) was quickly added Pd/C (498 mg, 4.68 mmol) then the solution was placed under a dihydrogen atmosphere and was stirred at room temperature for 24 h. The mixture was filtered on a celite pad and concentrated under reduced pressure. The desired product **1** was obtained as a white solid (500 mg, quant., α/β : 40/60).

R_f = 0.81 (DCM/MeOH 8:2); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ (ppm): 4.77 (d, 1H, J = 2.9 Hz, $\text{H}_{1-\alpha}$), 4.45 (dd, 1H, J = 1.9, 9.7 Hz, $\text{H}_{1-\beta}$), 3.86 (m, 2H, H_3), 3.79 (m, 2H, H_6), 3.68 (m, 2H, H_6), 3.55 (ddd, 1H, J = 5.1, 8.2, 12.0 Hz, H_5), 3.48 (s, 3H, H_7), 3.33 (s, 3H, H_7), 3.19 (m, 3H, H_5 , $\text{H}_{4-\alpha/\beta}$), 2.10 (ddd, 1H, J = 1.9, 5.1, 12.4 Hz, $\text{H}_{2-\alpha}$), 2.04 (ddd, 1H, J = 1.2, 5.2, 13.0 Hz, $\text{H}_{2-\alpha}$), 1.59 (ddd, 1H, J = 3.6, 11.7, 13.0 Hz, $\text{H}_{2-\beta}$), 1.45 (m, 1H, $\text{H}_{2-\beta}$); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CD_3OD) δ (ppm): 102.2 ($\text{C}_{1-\beta}$), 99.7 ($\text{C}_{1-\alpha}$), 78.0, 73.8 (2C, C_5), 73.2 (2C, C_4), 72.5, 69.9 (2C, C_3), 62.9 (C_6), 62.8 (C_6), 56.8 (C_7), 54.9 (C_7), 40.3 (C_2), 38.8 (C_2); HRMS-ESI $^+$ (m/z): found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 201.0725, calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ 201.0742.

▪ Methyl 2-deoxy- β -D-galactopyranoside **2**

Methyl 2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-(benzyl)- α/β -D-galactopyranoside **2.1**

2.1

To a solution of commercially available 3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl-D-galactal (2.0 g, 4.80 mmol) in anhydrous acetonitrile (20 mL) were added anhydrous MeOH (194 μ L, 4.80 mmol) and quickly ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) (53 mg, 0.10 mmol). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 36 h under Argon atmosphere, then the mixture was treated with diethyl ether (40 mL) and washed with sat. NaHCO_3 (40 mL x3) and sat. sodium chloride (40 mL x2). The organic layer was dried over MgSO_4 , filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by flash chromatography column (SiO_2 , petroleum ether/AcOEt 9:1) to afford **2.1** α product as a viscous liquid (764 mg, 35 %) and β product as a viscous liquid (298 mg, 14 %).

α product:

$R_f = 0.43$ (EP/AcOEt 9:1); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.47-7.32 (m, 15H, H_{Ar}), 4.93 (d, 1H, $J = 11.6$ Hz, CH_2Ph), 4.88 (d, 1H, $J = 3.0$ Hz, H_1), 4.62 (m, 1H, CH_2Ph), 4.59 (s, 2H, CH_2Ph), 4.53 (m, 1H, CH_2Ph), 4.43 (d, 1H, $J = 11.8$ Hz, CH_2Ph), 4.34 (m, 1H, H_1), 3.90 (m, 3H, H_4 , H_5 , H_3), 3.59 (dt, 2H, $J = 2.2$, 4.2 Hz, H_6), 3.32 (s, 3H, H_7), 2.23 (td, 1H, $J = 3.3$, 12.5 Hz, H_2), 2.00 (dd, 1H, $J = 4.5$, 12.7 Hz, H_2'); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 139.0 (1C, C_q), 138.7 (1C, C_q), 138.3 (1C, C_q), 127.7 (15C, CH_{Ar}), 99.1 (C_1), 74.9 (C_3), 74.4 (CH_2Ph), 73.6 (CH_2Ph), 73.1 (C_4), 70.6 (CH_2Ph), 70.0 (C_5), 69.8 (C_6), 55.0 (C_7), 31.2 (C_2).

β product:

$R_f = 0.28$ (EP/AcOEt 9:1); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.48-7.17 (m, 15H, H_{Ar}), 4.93 (d, 1H, $J = 11.8$ Hz, CH_2Ph), 4.64 (d, 1H, $J = 11.8$ Hz, CH_2Ph), 4.59 (s, 2H, CH_2Ph), 4.48 (d, 1H, $J = 11.8$ Hz, CH_2Ph), 4.43 (d, 1H, $J = 11.8$ Hz, CH_2Ph), 4.34 (m, 1H, H_1), 3.84 (d, 1H, $J = 1.9$ Hz, H_4), 3.64 (m, 2H, H_6), 3.55 (ddd, 1H, $J = 2.5$, 5.8, 9.9 Hz, H_5), 3.47 (s, 3H, H_7), 3.46 (m, 1H, H_3), 2.08 (dd, 1H, $J = 5.2$, 7.7 Hz, H_2), 2.05 (d, 1H, $J = 1.9$ Hz, H_2'); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 138.9 (C_q), 138.3 (C_q), 138.1 (C_q), 127.9 (15C, CH_{Ar}), 101.4 (C_1), 77.3 (C_5), 74.2 (CH_2Ph), 74.1 (C_3), 73.6 (CH_2Ph), 71.6 (C_4), 70.3 (CH_2Ph), 69.3 (C_6), 56.4 (C_7), 32.7 (C_2); **HRMS-ESI⁺ (m/z):** found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 471.2136, calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_5$ 471.2092.

Analytical data in agreement with literature [1].

Methyl 2-deoxy- β -D-galactopyranoside **2**

2

To a solution of methyl 2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α/β -D-galactopyranoside **2.1** (764 mg, 1.7 mmol) in anhydrous MeOH (150 mL) was added Pd/C (254 mg, 2.38 mmol), then the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 24 h under a dihydrogen atmosphere. The mixture was filtered on a celite pad and concentrated under reduced pressure to give the desired product **2** as a white solid (300 mg, quant.).

R_f = 0.73 (DCM/MeOH 8:2); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ (ppm): 4.80 (d, 1H, J = 3.3 Hz, H_1), 3.90 (ddd, 1H, J = 3.0, 5.0, 12.0 Hz, H_3), 3.76 (d, 1H, J = 2.8 Hz, H_4), 3.68 (m, 3H, H_6 , H_6' , H_5), 3.33 (s, 3H, H_7), 1.93 (td, 1H, J = 3.8, 12.6 Hz, H_2), 1.75 (ddt, 1H, J = 1.1, 5.1, 12.8 Hz, H_2'); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CD_3OD) δ (ppm): 98.7 (C_1), 70.9 (C_5), 68.2 (C_4), 65.2 (C_3), 61.9 (C_6), 53.6 (C_7), 32.2 (C_2).

Analytical data in agreement with literature [2].

III. Ion study in superacidic media

- General Procedure A for ion *in situ* NMR analysis at low temperature

To a magnetically stirred mixture of HF/SbF₅ (1 mL, SbF₅ mol% = 22), maintained at -50°C, was added the substrate (~ 30 mg). After 5 minutes, the mixture was introduced in a Teflon® NMR tube which was inserted into a classical glass NMR tube containing acetone-d₆ as an external standard.

- 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosylium cation **A**

The polyprotonated cation **A** was obtained from commercially available methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -L-arabinofuranoside according to general procedure A.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, ((CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 10.35 (s, 2H, H'), 10.08 (s, 2H, H'), 8.94 (s, 1H, H₁), 7.60 (br. s, 2H, H'), 5.41 (d, 1H, J = 8.1 Hz, H₄), 4.42 (br. s, 1H, H₃), 3.88 (d, 1H, J = 13.7 Hz, H₅), 3.53 (br. s, 1H, H_{5'}), 3.37 (m, 2H, H₂ - H_{2'}), 2.81 (s, 3H, CH₃-methyloxonium); **¹³C NMR (100 MHz, ((CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm):** 230.4 (C₁), 104.3 (C₄), 73.0 (C₃), 65.8 (C₅), 59.9 (CH₃, C_{methyloxonium}), 49.5 (C₂).

^1H NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 400 MHz) of oxonium ion A

^{13}C NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 100 MHz) of oxonium ion A

COSY NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of oxonium ion A

HSQC NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of oxonium ion A

2-deoxyglucopyranosylium cation **B**

The polyprotonated cation **B** was obtained from methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1** according to general procedure **A**.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 10.20 (br. s, H'), 9.10 (s, 1H, H₁), 7.69 (d, 3H, J = 3.58 Hz, H', H_{methyloxonium}), 4.96 (s, 1H, H₄), 4.85 (s, 1H, H₃), 4.57 (s, 1H, H₅), 3.83 (m, 2H, H₆), 3.46 (m, 1H, H₂), 3.35 (m, 1H, H_{2'}), 2.86 (s, 3H, CH₃-methyloxonium); **¹³C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm):** 231.5 (C₁), 97.8 (C₅), 73.7 (C₃), 72.2 (C₄), 66.5 (C₆), 59.9 (CH₃, C_{methyloxonium}), 50.8 (C₂).

^1H NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 400 MHz) of oxonium ion B

^{13}C NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 100 MHz) of oxonium ion B

COSY NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of oxonium ion B

HSQC NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of oxonium ion B

2-deoxygalactopyranosylium cation C

The polyprotonated cation **C** was obtained from methyl 2-deoxy- β -D-galactopyranoside **2** according to general procedure **A**.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 10.41 (br. s, H'), 9.10 (s, 1H, H₁), 7.70 (H', H_{methyloxonium}), 5.37 (s, 1H, H₄), 4.74 (br. s, 1H, H₃), 4.55 (br. s, 1H, H₅), 3.98 (br. s, 1H, H₆), 3.81 (br. s, 1H, H_{6'}), 3.62 (br. s, 1H, H₂), 3.47 (br. s, 1H, H_{2'}), 2.86 (s, 3H, CH₃-methyloxonium); **¹³C NMR (100 MHz, ((CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm):** 233.4 (C₁), 102.2 (C₄), 75.2 (C₅), 73.4 (C₃), 65.8 (C₆), 60.2 (CH₃, C_{methyloxonium}), 50.0 (C₂).

^1H NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 400 MHz) of oxonium ion C

^{13}C NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 100 MHz) of oxonium ion C

COSY NMR ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$) of oxonium ion C

HSQC NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of oxonium ion C

IV. Stability test of cations

- Cation A stability from -50 to 20°C in superacid environment

Stability of cation **A** for 360 min

- Cation **B** stability from -50 to 20°C in superacid environment

Stability of cation **B** for 360 min

- Cation **C** stability from -50 to 20°C in superacid environment

Stability of cation **C** for 360 min

V. Study of the 1,2,4-butanetriol ion D in superacidic media

Study of cation D in a superacid medium

The polyprotonated compound **D** was obtained from commercially available 1,2,4-butanetriol according to general procedure A.

¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 9.76 (s, 4H, H'), 8.76 (s, 2H, H'), 3.92 (br. s, 1H, H₂), 3.44 (br. s, 4H, H₁ and H₄), 1.09 (br. s, 2H, H₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 78.9 (C₂), 70.1 (C₁), 68.6 (C₄), 26.2 (C₃).

¹H NMR spectrum ((CD₃)₂CO, 400 MHz) of **D**:

¹³C NMR spectrum ((CD₃)₂CO, 100 MHz) of **D**:

COSY NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of D:

HSQC NMR ((CD₃)₂CO) of D:

▪ Cation D stability from -50 to 20°C in superacid environment

Stability of cation **D** for 360 min

VI. Side products formation in superacidic media

Side product: cation **B.1**

Degradation began to be observed during accumulation of oxocarbenium **B** at 5°C. A mixture of oxocarbenium ion **B** and an elimination product **B.1** was observed.

Elimination product **B.1**:

¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 8.87 (d, 1H, *J* = 3.1 Hz, H₁), 8.10 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.7 Hz, H₂), 7.90 (s, H', H_{methyloxonium}), 6.63 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.5 Hz, H₃), 5.62 (br. s, 1H, H₄), 4.71 (m, 1H, H₅), 3.97-3.83 (m, 2H, H₆).

¹H NMR spectrum ((CD₃)₂CO, 400 MHz) of cation **B.1**

▪ Side product: cation **C.1**

Extensive degradation began to be observed during accumulation of oxocarbenium **C** at 10°C, to give the elimination product **C.1**.

Elimination product **C.1**:

¹H NMR (400 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm): 8.93 (s, 1H, H₁), 8.15 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.5 Hz, H₂), 7.86 (s, H', H_{methyloxonium}), 6.67 (d, 1H, *J* = 5.4 Hz, H₃), 5.56 (d, 1H, *J* = 11.7 Hz, H₄), 4.69 (dd, 1H, *J* = 6.1, 9.1 Hz, H₅), 4.18 (d, 1H, *J* = 14.4 Hz, H₆), 4.08 (dd, 1H, *J* = 8.0, 14.5 Hz, H_{6'}); **¹³C NMR (100 MHz, (CD₃)₂CO) δ (ppm):** 211.2 (C₁), 178.3 (C₃), 134.0 (C₂), 99.1 (C₄), 74.0 (C₅), 66.7 (C₆), 60.1 (CH₃, C_{methyloxonium}).

^1H NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 400 MHz) of cation C.1

^{13}C NMR spectrum ($(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$, 100 MHz) of cation C.1

VII. Deuteration studies

General Procedure B for the deuteration in superacid environment

To a mixture of HF/SbF₅ (22mol% SbF₅) in a teflon tube were added the unprotected carbohydrate (1.0 equiv) and cyclohexane-d₁₂ (4 equiv) at -40°C. The mixture was magnetically stirred at 0°C for 5 min. Hydrolysis was performed on ice and resin A-26 was added until pH = 7. The mixture was filtered on celite and the solution was concentrated. Then, the mixture was washed twice with DCM (10 mL) and the aqueous phase was concentrated and co-concentrated with toluene to give the desired deuterated product.

2-deoxy-L-[1-²H]-arabinofuranoside **A.1**

Product **A.1** (26 mg, 54 %) was obtained from methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -L-arabinofuranoside (60 mg, 0.40 mmol) according to general procedure **B**.

R_f = 0.61 (DCM/MeOH 8:2); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ (ppm): 4.20 (dt, 1H, J = 3.0, 3.0, 6.1 Hz, H₃), 3.92 (dd, 1H, J = 3.6, 8.0 Hz, H₁), 3.74 (td, 1H, J = 3.0, 5.0, 4.9 Hz, H₄), 3.55 (dd, 1H, J = 4.6, 11.7 Hz, H₅), 3.51 (dd, 1H, J = 5.3, 11.7 Hz, H_{5'}), 2.07 (ddd, 1H, J = 6.6, 7.6, 13.1 Hz, H₂), 1.84 (ddd, 1H, J = 3.4, 3.0, 12.8 Hz, H₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CD₃OD) δ (ppm): 88.1 (C₄), 73.8 (C₃), 67.7 (t, J = 22.3 Hz, C₁), 63.6 (C₅), 35.8 (C₂); HRMS-ESI⁺ (m/z): found [M+Na]⁺ 142.0585, calcd. for C₅H₉DO₃Na 142.0592.

NOESY (298K, 800MHz) NMR (CD₃OD) of 2-deoxy-L-[1-²H]-arabinofuranoside A.1

H₁ has no NOE with H₄, the deuterium must be pointing up

▪ 2-deoxy- α/β -D-[1-²H]-glucopyranoside **B.2**

Product **B.2** (38 mg, 76 %) was obtained from methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1** (60 mg, 0.34 mmol) according to general procedure **B**.

R_f = 0.76 (DCM/MeOH 8:2); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD) δ (ppm): 4.42 (td, 1H, J = 3.5, 2.1, 1.1 Hz, H₃), 3.97 (dd, 1H, J = 7.6, 8.6 Hz, H₁), 3.84 (dt, 1H, J = 8.4, 6.2, 3.2 Hz, H₅), 3.76 (dd, 1H, J = 3.2, 11.4 Hz, H_{6'}), 3.56 (dd, 1H, J = 6.2, 11.4 Hz, H₆), 3.53 (dd, 1H, J = 3.3, 8.3 Hz, H₄), 2.12 (ddd, 1H, J = 5.0, 9.0, 13.5 Hz, H_{2'}), 1.91 (ddd, 1H, J = 1.2, 8.2, 13.3 Hz, H₂); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CD₃OD) δ (ppm): 83.6 (C₄), 72.5 (C₃), 71.4 (C₅), 67.2 (t, J = 22.5 Hz, C₁), 65.5 (C₆), 36.0 (C₂); HRMS-ESI⁺ (m/z): found [M+Na]⁺ 172.0686, calcd. for C₆H₁₁DO₄Na 172.0692.

NOESY (298K, 500MHz) NMR (CD₃OD) of 2-deoxy- α/β -D-[1-²H]-glucopyranoside B.2

H₁ has NOE with H₅, the deuterium must be pointing up

2-deoxy-β-D-[1-²H]-galactopyranoside **C.2**

Product **C.2** (15 mg, 30 %) was obtained from methyl 2-deoxy-β-D-galactopyranoside **2** (60 mg, 0.34 mmol) according to general procedure **B**.

R_f = 0.51 (DCM/MeOH 8:2); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CD_3OD) δ (ppm): 4.31 (ddd, 1H, J = 3.3, 6.6, 3.4 Hz, H_3), 3.94 (dd, 1H, J = 3.9, 8.0 Hz, H_1), 3.70 (dd, 1H, J = 3.2, 3.3 Hz, H_4), 3.64 (m, 1H, H_5), 3.57 (dd, 1H, J = 3.5, 10.0 Hz, H_6), 3.57 (dd, 1H, J = <1, 8.5 Hz, H_6'), 2.09 (ddd, 1H, J = 7.3, 6.1, 13.0 Hz, H_2), 1.82 (dt, 1H, J = 3.6, 3.6, 12.7 Hz, H_2); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (100 MHz, CD_3OD) δ (ppm): 87.6 (C_4), 74.3 (C_3), 73.2 (C_5), 67.9 (t, J = 22.2 Hz, C_1), 64.7 (C_6), 36.2 (C_2); HRMS-ESI⁺ (m/z): found $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$ 172.0686, calcd. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{DO}_4\text{Na}$ 172.0692.

NOESY (298K, 500MHz) NMR (CD₃OD) of 2-deoxy-β-D-[1-²H]-galactopyranoside C.2

H₁ has no NOE with H₅, the deuterium must be pointing down

VIII. NMR Spectra

■ Methyl 2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1.1**

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of **1.1**

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of **1.1**

▪ Methyl 2-deoxy- α/β -D-glucopyranoside **1**

^1H NMR spectrum (CD_3OD , 400 MHz) of **1**

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CD_3OD , 100 MHz) of **1**

■ Methyl 2-deoxy-3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl- α/β -D-galactopyranoside **2.1**

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of 2.1: α product

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of 2.1: α product

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of 2.1: β product

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of 2.1: β product

■ **Methyl 2-deoxy-β-D-galactopyranoside 2**

¹H NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 400 MHz) of 2

¹³C NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 100 MHz) of 2

■ 2-deoxy-L-[1-²H]-arabinofuranoside A.1

¹H NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 400 MHz) of A.1

¹³C NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 100 MHz) of A.1

■ **2-deoxy-α/β-D-[1-²H]-glucopyranoside B.2**

¹H NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 400 MHz) of B.2

¹³C NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 100 MHz) of B.2

2-deoxy-β-D-[1-²H]-galactopyranoside C.2

¹H NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 400 MHz) of C.2

¹³C NMR spectrum (CD₃OD, 100 MHz) of C.2

IX. DFT calculations

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed in Gaussian 094 Revision E.01.5. The molecular models for species **A**, **B**, and **C** were built in GaussView5.0.9. Initial geometries were generated considering the $^3J(\text{H,H})$ coupling constants. Geometry optimizations were carried out at the b3lyp/6-31+g level, and NMR coupling predicted through GIAO/DFT calculations at b3lyp/6-311+g(d,p).

▪ 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation

For the 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation (**A**), the model was built with protonation of hydroxyls at positions 3 and 5, as observed experimentally, resulting in a total +3 charge. The ring puckering of the structure obtained from the optimization calculation resulted a **3E -like conformation**. The GIAO/DFT predicted $^3J(\text{H,H})$ are compared with the experimental ones in the table below.

NMR $^3J(\text{H,H})$ coupling constants (Hz)		
Proton pair	Model (DFT)*	Experimental [§]
H1,H2	0,6	≤ 2
H1,H2´	0,6	≤ 2
H2,H3	6,7	7,5
H2´,H3	0,1	1,9
H3,H4	0,8	≤ 2
H4,H5	9,9	8,5
H4,H5´	4,5	< 2

* GIAO/DFT predicted for model on the left, as obtained by DFT optimization in Gaussian.

§from ^1H -NMR spectrum at -50°C .

▪ 2-deoxy-D-glucosyl cation

For the 2-deoxy-D-glucosyl cation (**B**), the model was built with protonation of hydroxyls at position 6, as observed experimentally, resulting in a +2 total charge. The ring puckering of the structure obtained from the optimization calculation (below) had the Cremer-Pople coordinates (φ , θ , Q) (30.7° , 127.9° , 0.52) (as calculated by <http://enzyme13.bt.a.u-tokyo.ac.jp/CP/>), thus a **E_4 conformation**. The GIAO/DFT predicted $^3J(\text{H,H})$ are compared with the experimental ones in the table below.

NMR $^3J(\text{H,H})$ coupling constants (Hz)

Proton pair	Model (DFT)*	Experimental [§]
H1,H2	1,9	< 1
H1,H2´	1,5	< 1
H2,H3	1,7	< 1
H2´,H3	3,5	5,8
H3,H4	5,4	5,2
H4,H5	0,7	3,6
H5,H6	0,7	3,1
H5,H6´	8,3	7,6

* GIAO/DFT predicted for model on the left, as obtained by DFT optimization in Gaussian.

[§]from $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum at -20°C .

▪ 2-deoxy-D-galactosyl cation

For the 2-deoxy-D-galactosyl cation (**C**), the model was built with protonation of hydroxyls at position 6, as observed experimentally, resulting in a +2 total charge. The ring puckering of the structure obtained from the optimization calculation (below) had the Cremer-Pople coordinates (φ , θ , Q) (236.9° , 52.5° , 0.46) (as calculated by <http://enzyme13.bt.a.u-tokyo.ac.jp/CP/>), thus a **4E conformation**. The GIAO/DFT predicted $^3J(\text{H,H})$ are compared with the experimental ones in the table below.

NMR $^3J(\text{H,H})$ coupling constants (Hz)

Proton pair	Model (DFT)*	Experimental [§]
H1,H2	0,3	< 1
H1,H2´	0,1	< 1
H2,H3	4,1	2,1
H2´,H3	5,6	7,9
H3,H4	3,1	≤ 4
H4,H5	1,9	≤ 4
H5,H6	1,2	≤ 4
H5,H6´	7,2	8,6

* GIAO/DFT predicted for model on the left, as obtained by DFT optimization in Gaussian.

[§]from $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectrum at -50°C .

X. Superacid force field validation

To assess the quality of our in-house parametrized superacid force field, we compared the properties of intramolecular bond distances calculated from classical MD simulations with reference data obtained from *ab initio* MD simulations. First, the bond distances of the superacid molecules were monitored along the whole simulation, in which the H-F bond distance of the HF molecule has a value of 0.93 Å. This value is comparable to the ones obtained by Kim et. al. [3] using CPMD (0.93 Å), as well as the experimental value (0.92 Å) [4]. The F-H covalent bond distance increases for H_2F^+ (0.99 Å), a value comparable to the one reported by Sophy et. al. using *ab initio* methods (~ 1.02 Å) [5]. The Sb-F bond distance has the same average value as the one obtained by Kim et. al. [3] (0.92 Å). Note that in classical MD is not possible to distinguish between the two types of Sb-F bonds, one in which the fluorine atom forms a hydrogen bond with HF molecules and the other one in which it does not (their corresponding values being 1.95 Å and 1.90 Å, respectively).

Figure S1. Bond lengths (in Å) of the parametrized superacid molecules; HF, H_2F^+ and SbF_6^- along the classical MD simulation. The average value is indicated by a blue line.

The classical MD energies, volume and density of the simulations were also monitored. Equilibration was reached at a volume of $2 \cdot 10^5 \text{ \AA}^3$ and density of $2.4 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$. The last value is in-between the experimental density of liquid SbF_5 ($2.99 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and HF ($0.987 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) at ambient conditions [6].

The structural properties of the solvent were analysed using radial pair distribution functions, $g(r)$. The $g(r)$ of H atoms (from HF molecules) and F atoms (from SbF_6^- molecules) was compared with that of H (from HF molecules) and F (from HF molecules). The large peak at approximately 0.9 Å corresponds to the H-F bond distance (HF molecules). The peak at ~ 1.6 Å corresponds to the F atoms of the SbF_6^- anion, which form hydrogen bonds with nearby HF molecules. It coincides with the second peak of $g(\text{H}-\text{F}_{\text{HF}})$, which also corresponds to F atoms that are engaged in hydrogen bond interactions, in this case between different HF molecules. These results agree with the ones reported by Kim et. al. [3] using *ab initio* MD, with the only difference being the disappearance of a shoulder peak for $g(\text{H}-\text{F}_{\text{HF}})$ and a small peak for $g(\text{H}-\text{F}_{\text{SbF}_6^-})$, both at 1.2 Å. These two (here non-observed) peaks correspond to the interaction

between an excess proton with either HF or SbF_6^- molecules. Therefore, they are the manifestation of the existence of a contact ion pair. The formation of such contact ion pairs cannot be described by classical MD.

Figure S2. Radial pair distribution function, $g(r)$, for H (HF) and F (HF) solvent molecules (black line) and for H (HF) and F (SbF_6^-) solvent molecules (blue line).

XI. Computational methodology

▪ Conformational FELs in gas-phase

The conformational FELs of the 2-deoxy-D-galactosyl, 2-deoxy-D-glucosyl and 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cations in gas phase were computed with DFT-based MD, within the Car-Parrinello (CP) method [7], using the CPMD code [8]. The systems were enclosed in isolated cubic boxes of $16.0 \times 15.0 \times 15.0 \text{ \AA}^3$, $14.8 \times 13.5 \times 10.3 \text{ \AA}^3$ and $12.5 \times 12.5 \times 12.5 \text{ \AA}^3$, respectively. A fictitious electron mass of 850 and 500 atomic units (a.u.) was used for the CP Lagrangian for the pyranosyl and furanosyl cations, respectively, and a time step of 0.12 fs was used to ensure the adiabaticity of the fictitious kinetic energy of the electrons ($\leq 10^{-5}$ a.u./atom). The Kohn-Sham orbitals were expanded in a plane wave (PW) basis set, with a kinetic energy cutoff of 70 Ry. *Ab initio* pseudopotentials, generated within the Troullier-Martins scheme, were employed. The Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhoff generalized gradient-corrected approximation [9] was selected in view of its good performance in the description of sugar conformational landscapes [11]. The metadynamics algorithm [12], provided by the Plumed2 plugin [13], was used to explore the conformational free energy landscape. In the case of the pyranosyl cations, the cartesian Cremer-Pople puckering coordinates, q_x , q_y and q_z , divided by the amplitude (Q) were taken as collective variables. In the case of the furanosyl cation, the pseudorotational phase (ϕ)

puckering coordinate [15] and a dihedral angle accounting for the rotation of the sugar hydroxymethyl group was used, since this group was found not to sample enough conformations otherwise (preliminary simulations). Initially, the height of the Gaussian-like potential was set to 0.6 kcal·mol⁻¹ and Gaussian potentials were added every 250 (pyranosyl cations) and 500 (furanosyl cation) MD steps. Once the whole free energy space was explored, the height of the Gaussian terms was reduced to 0.2 kcal·mol⁻¹ to facilitate convergence of the FEL. The width of the collective variables was set according to their oscillations in the free dynamics (0.05, 0.05 and 0.015 rad for pyranosyl cations and 0.035 and 0.1 rad for the furanosyl cation). The simulations were stopped when energy differences among wells remain constant and the standard deviations of the oscillations were below 0.5 kcal·mol⁻¹, which correspond to 26301, 16500 and 35171 deposited Gaussians for 2-deoxygalactosyl, 2-deoxyglucosyl and 2-deoxyarabinofuranosyl cations, respectively. The FEL of the pyranosyl cations was projected against the polar coordinates θ and ϕ for representation purposes, using the reweighting method described in Branduardi et. al. [16]. In the case of the furanosyl cation, the FEL was projected into the ϕ coordinate.

▪ Parametrization of a superacid force field

The anionic species present in the superacid solutions were identified by ¹⁹F NMR spectroscopy (see Figure S3). The Sb-based molecules found in the solution were found to be a mixture of SbF₆⁻ and Sb₂F₁₁⁻, with a major concentration of SbF₆⁻. We decided to simplify the superacid solvent by modelling only SbF₆⁻, together with H₂F⁺ molecules, which are also in the superacid solution. To reproduce the molar percentage of SbF₅ used experimentally (21.6%), while keeping system neutrality, HF were also modelled. The following parametrization approach was used:

SbF₆⁻ molecule: MCPB.py [17] from AmberTools16[18] was used, with no differentiation between the small and large models. First, we prepared the input files for Gaussian (version g09 [19]), followed by force constant calculation and the Merz-Kollman RESP charge calculation. We omitted the geometry optimization step as we used the optimized structure obtained by Kim et. al. [3] with CPMD. Here, SbF₆⁻ exhibits an octahedral coordination, with an average Sb-F bond length of 0.925Å when surrounded by HF molecules. Force constant and RESP charge calculations were obtained at the HF/LANL2DZ level of theory for Sb and HF/6-31G* for F. Subsequently, we generated the force-field parameters using MCPB.py and the Seminario method [20]. Afterwards, we used ChgModB to perform the RESP charge fitting and generate the mol2 files.

H₂F⁺ and HF molecules: The Force Field Tool Kit (ffTK) [21] plugin, within VMD [22], was used. This software gives a complete set of CHARMM-compatible parameters, which we converted to Amber format. The LJ/VdW parameters were extracted from the par_all36_cgenff.prm file. Afterwards, the geometry was optimized with Gaussian (g09 [19]) at the MP2/6-31G* level of theory. The next step of the ffTK workflow consists of deriving the partial charges on atoms. In the CHARMM convention, partial charges are taken from several QM calculations in which the molecule interacts with a water molecule [23]. In contrast, AMBER charges are obtained from a fitting to the restrained electrostatic potential of the molecule [22]. Therefore, as we were following the AMBER convention, we derived the RESP charges at the HF/6-31G* level of theory and, afterwards, we used the antechamber plugin [25] to obtain the prep file with all the corresponding partial charges. Finally, the Hessian matrix was computed

at the MP2/6-31G* level of theory to obtain bond and angle parameters (the fTK plugin was used for this purpose).

Figure S3. ^{19}F NMR of superacid media

The parameters obtained are the following:

Atom	RESP charge
Sb	1.645599
F1 _{SbF6-}	-0.441021
F2 _{SbF6-}	-0.441045
F3 _{SbF6-}	-0.440906
F4 _{SbF6-}	-0.440754
F5 _{SbF6-}	-0.440922
F6 _{SbF6-}	-0.440950
F _{HF}	-0.454771
H _{HF}	0.454771
F _{H2F+}	-0.179553
H _{H2F+}	0.589777

Distance	K_r (kcal·mol ⁻¹ ·Å ⁻²)	r_{eq} (Å)
F-H (HF)	588.5	0.9340
F-H (H ₂ F ⁺)	415.9	0.9870
Sb-F (SbF ₆ ⁻)	174	1.925

Angle	K_{θ} (kcal·mol ⁻¹ ·rad ⁻²)	θ_{eq} (degrees)
H-F-H (H ₂ F ⁺)	38.417	111.183
F2-Sb-F1 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	132.09	90.02
F3-Sb-F1 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	131.89	90.02
F3-Sb-F2 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	123.24	179.96
F4-Sb-F1 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	121.60	179.97
F4-Sb-F2 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	132.10	89.96
F4-Sb-F3 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	131.91	90.00
F5-Sb-F1 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	133.62	90.02
F5-Sb-F2 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	130.96	90.01
F5-Sb-F3 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	130.82	90.00
F5-Sb-F4 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	133.57	89.97
F6-Sb-F1 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	133.57	90.02
F6-Sb-F2 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	130.95	89.99
F6-Sb-F3 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	130.85	90.00
F6-Sb-F4 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	133.53	89.99
F6-Sb-F5 (SbF ₆ ⁻)	132.30	179.96

Atom	VdW radius (Å)	ϵ (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
Sb	2.21	0.449	Adopted from atom type Sb ₃ ⁺³ from UFF (Rappe et al. JACS, 114, (1992))
F _{SbF6-}	1.75	0.061	Gough et al. JCC, 13, (1992)
F _{HF}	1.63	0.135	Adopted from par_all36_cgenff
F _{H2F+}	1.63	0.135	Adopted from par_all36_cgenff

■ Conformational FELs in superacid media

Classical MD simulations were set up employing the program LEaP that is included in the Amber suite of programs, using our superacid media force field parameters. The 2-deoxygalactosyl, 2-deoxyglucosyl and 2-deoxyarabinofuranosyl cations with protonated hydroxyl groups were parametrized using antechamber [26] and gaff [25]. As Amber is not designed for small periodic systems, large solvation boxes were used. The glycosyl cations were separately solvated by 861/862 SbF₆⁻, 857/858 H₂F⁺ and 2270/2269 HF molecules for pyranosyl/furanosyl cations, respectively. The MD simulations were performed using Amber14 [27]. The system was thermally equilibrated at 300K prior to the MD equilibration in the NPT ensemble, followed by a production phase between 50 and 200 ns. The SHAKE algorithm, with an integration step of 2 fs, was used. One frame from the production MD simulation was taken to set up the forthcoming QM/MM MD metadynamics simulations.

The method developed by Laio et. al. [28] was used. The quantum (QM) region was selected as the corresponding polyprotonated glycosyl cation (24 atoms for pyranosyl cations and 19 atoms for the furanosyl cation). The Car-Parrinello MD [7] method with the PBE functional [9] was used to describe the QM region, as used previously for the isolated molecules. The molecular mechanics (MM) region was taken as the superacid solvent (3998 atoms for pyranosyl and 3999 atoms for furanosyl). The Amber force-field, as previously used in the classical MD simulations, was used to describe the MM region. The electrostatic interactions between the QM and MM regions were handled via a fully Hamiltonian scheme base on a multilayer [28]. The radii of the three different layers, called NN, MIX and ESP, were chosen as 12, 12 and 22 a.u., respectively, after testing them according to reference [29]. The 2-deoxygalactosyl, 2-deoxyglucosyl and 2-deoxyarabinofuranosyl cations were enclosed in an isolated cubic box of 13.7 x 12.3 x 12.3 Å³, 13.07 x 12.5 x 12.4 Å³ and 12.6 x 11.6 x 12.9 Å³, respectively. A fictitious electron mass of 500 atomic units (a.u.) and a timestep of 3 a.u. were used for the CP Lagrangian. The Kohn-Sham orbitals were expanded in a plane wave basis set with a kinetic energy cut-off of 70 Ry. *Ab initio* pseudopotentials, generated within the Troullier-Martins scheme, were employed. After equilibrating the systems within the QM/MM scheme, we performed metadynamics simulations [12], using the Plumed 2 plugin [13], to explore the conformational FELs of each superacid-solvated glycosyl cation. The Cremer-Pople puckering coordinates qx, qy and qz divided by the amplitude (Q), as well as the hydroxymethyl dihedral angle (for the pyranosyl cations) or the pseudorotational phase (ϕ) and the hydroxymethyl dihedral angle (for the furanosyl cation) were used as collective variables (CVs). The height of the gaussian-like potential was set to 0.6 (pyranosyl) and 0.3 (furanosyl) kcal·mol⁻¹ and added every 250 molecular dynamics steps. The width of the collective variables was set according to their oscillations in the free dynamics, which corresponds to 0.05, 0.05, 0.015 and 0.1 rad (pyranosyl) and 0.035 and 0.1 rad (furanosyl). The simulations were stopped when 44000, 12824 and 20848 Gaussians were deposited. Structures with specific glycosyl cation

conformations were extracted from the FELs and used to compute the properties of these cations in superacid media.

■ Conformational FELs on-enzyme

The 2-deoxygalactosyl cation conformational FEL was computed in the active site of β -galactocerebrosidase, GALC, whose reaction mechanism was computed in reference [30] and a snapshot of the TS of the hydrolysis reaction was taken. The conformational FEL of the 2-deoxyglucosyl cation was computed in the active site of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Gas2 β -glucanase, ScGas2, whose mechanism was analyzed in reference [31]. In that study, MD simulations were performed to unravel the hydrogen bond interactions involving the C2 hydroxyl group. It was found that the 2-OH group can adopt two conformations, either interacting with the nucleophile residue (*on* configuration) or interacting with a solvent water molecule (*off* configuration) with populations around 50%. We chose the TS of the glycosylation reaction with the 2-OH in the *off* configuration due to a higher similarity in the active site interactions when the sugar lacks the 2-OH group, as is the case in the glycosyl cations under investigation here. In the case of the 2-deoxyarabinofuranosyl cation conformational FEL on-enzyme, the TS of the hydrolysis reaction in the active site of *Aspergillus Kawachii* AbfB (AkAbfB) was taken. The hydroxyl in C2 was replaced manually with a hydrogen in the TS snapshot and a QM/MM MD equilibration was performed in each system.

The values of the electrostatic layers NN, MIX and ESP were set to 20,20 and 38 and 12, 12 and 16 a.u. for the pyranosyl cases (2-deoxygalactosyl and 2-deoxyglucosyl cations) and 10, 10 and 18 a.u. for the furanosyl case. In the 2-deoxygalactosyl simulation, the QM region included only the cation itself in -1 leading to a total number of 21 quantum atoms; in the 2-deoxyglucosyl simulation, the QM region included the glycosyl cation at the -1 subsite and half ring of the saccharide placed in the -2 subsite, leading to a total number of 32 quantum atoms (including capping hydrogens) and in the furanosyl simulation, the QM region only included the carbocation itself leading to 17 quantum atoms. By including the cation in the QM region while excluding the catalytic residues, the reaction cannot evolve, thus the system is kept in a “TS-like” state.

The QM atoms were enclosed in an isolated supercell of size $12.4 \times 12.4 \times 13.6 \text{ \AA}^3$, $15.3 \times 15.3 \times 15.3 \text{ \AA}^3$ and $12.1 \times 12.1 \times 11.9 \text{ \AA}^3$ and a fictitious electron mass of 700 and 500 atomic units (a.u.), for the pyranosyl and furanosyl cases, respectively, and a time step of 5 a.u. was used for the QM/MM MD simulations. The CPMD setup done in all the previous systems was used. The cartesian Cremer-Pople puckering coordinates divided by the amplitude were used as CVs for the pyranosyl cations and the pseudorotational phase was used as CV for the furanosyl cation. The height of the gaussian-like potential was set to $0.6 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and these potentials were added every 250 or 500 (pyranosyl) or 500 (furanosyl) MD steps. Once the whole free energy spaces were explored, the height of the Gaussian terms were reduced to $0.2 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and the deposition time was increased to 1000 MD steps to facilitate convergence of the FEL. The width of the collective variables was set to 0.05, 0.05 and 0.04 rad (for the galactosyl cation), 0.05, 0.05 and 0.015 rad (for the glucosyl cation) and 0.05, 0.05 and 0.035 rad (for the furanosyl cation). The simulations were stopped after 1760, 1807 and 4998 deposited Gaussians.

▪ Reaction mechanism of α -L-arabinofuranosidase (AkAbfB)

The initial structure for the simulations was taken from *Aspergillus luchuensis* GH54 α -L-arabinofuranosidase E221Q mutated enzyme (PDB code 6SXR) at 1.64Å resolution. The mutation was reversed *in silico* and the classical MD simulation was set up employing the program LEaP included in the Amber suite [18] and the ff14SB protein force field [32] was used. The substrate was parametrized using gaff2 [25], solvated with explicit TIP3P water molecules [23] and neutralized with 21 sodium atoms. Classical MD simulation was performed using Amber16 [18]. A thermal equilibration to 300 K was done prior to the equilibration of dynamics in the NPT ensemble with a production phase of 48 ns.

The chemical reaction was computed by means of a QM/MM MD simulation using the method developed by Laio et. al. [28], the quantum region is treated using the PBE functional and Car-Parrinello MD whereas the molecular mechanics region is treated using the AMBER force field; when a covalent bond is placed in the QM-MM boundary, this is treated by saturating the QM region within a MD formalism parametrizing a boundary atom described by a pseudopotential. The electrostatic interactions between the QM and MM region are handled with two layers, NN and ESP regions. Metadynamics [12] was also implemented with the CPMD program (version 3.15.1) [8] and the Plumed package (version 2.3.3) [13]. The PNP-Araf substrate and the catalytic residues (Glu221 and Asp297) until their beta carbon were included in the QM region. The CVs chosen were the bonds to be broken and formed; the first CV corresponds to the formation of the covalent bond between the anomeric carbon of the PNP-Araf substrate and the nucleophile whereas the second CV quantifies the cleavage of the glycosidic bond. The proton transfer between the aglycon moiety and Asp297 (acid/base) was not included due to the relatively good leaving group character of the p-nitrophenol group ($pK_a = 7.15$), which made us think that the reaction would take place without leaving group protonation. The statistical error of the reaction free energy barrier was computed by launching several metadynamics simulations changing the Gaussian height and keeping all the other parameters constant [33]. This should be considered as an approximation to the statistical error of the metadynamics simulation, since only the Gaussian height (not the width) was varied. Each simulation was restarted from the point along the metadynamics run in which the reactants basin is half filled and its height was changed to 0.3, 0.5 and 0.63 kcal·mol⁻¹. The results showed that the reaction mechanism was not affected significantly by the change of the Gaussian height. The following parameters were used for the metadynamics simulations.

Table S1. Parameters of the QM/MM MD metadynamics simulation

Parameters	Value
Number of quantum atoms	50
Functional	PBE
Planewaves cutoff (Ry)	70
Atom pseudopotentials	Norm-conserving Martin Trouillers
Fictitious electronic mass (a.u.)	700
Time step (a.u.)	5
Size of the electrostatic regions (NN/ESP in a.u.)	14/22
Supercell size (Å)	19 x 15.6 x 16.9
CV1	Distance O _{Glu221} – C1
CV2	Distance C1 – glycosidic oxygen
Gaussian width (a.u.)	0.1 and 0.1
Gaussian height (kcal·mol ⁻¹)	0.31/0.5/0.63/1
Deposition time (MD steps)	300
Deposited gaussians	747
Simulation time (ps)	27

XII. Modelling glycosyl cations in superacid media

- Classical MD simulation results for the 2-deoxyglucosyl cation

Figure S4. Averaged occupation of SbF_6^- molecules along the classical MD simulation shown as transparent gray surfaces. One SbF_6^- molecule is represented using stick models for clarity. **(a)** Side and bottom views for the E_4 conformation. **(b)** Side and bottom views for the 4E conformation.

Figure S5. Radial pair distribution functions for the anomeric carbon and the oxygens of protonated hydroxyls of 2-deoxy-D-glucosyl cation with the solvent molecules, HF (blue line), H_2F^+ (green line) and SbF_6^- (red line). The two peaks at distances < 4 Å correspond to the radial distribution of F_{HF} and H_{HF} , respectively. The distance difference between these two peaks correspond to the H-F bond distance, ~ 0.9 Å. The distance between the first solvation shell of HF molecules and the glucosyl cation hydroxyls is ~ 1.5 Å. This distance is smaller compared to that involving the anomeric carbon due to their ability to create hydrogen bonds besides pure electrostatic interactions. The ring sugar in E_4 conformation in **a** or 4E conformation in **b**.

Figure S6. Interactions present in superacid media (SbF_6^- and HF molecules) with the glucosyl cation. Representative hydrogen bond/salt bridges interactions are represented as black dashed lines. **(a)** Sugar in E_4 conformation. **(b)** Sugar in 4E conformation.

■ Classical MD simulation results for 2-deoxygalactosyl cation

- **Figure S7.** Averaged occupation of SbF_6^- molecules along the classical MD simulation shown as transparent gray surfaces. One SbF_6^- molecule is represented using stick models for clarity. Side and bottom views are shown. The sugar is in the ${}^4\text{H}_3$ conformation.

Figure S8. Radial pair distribution functions for the anomeric carbon and the oxygens of protonated hydroxyls of the 2-deoxy-D-galactosyl cation with the solvent molecules, HF (blue line), H_2F^+ (green line) and SbF_6^- (red line).

Figure S9. Interactions between the galactosyl cation and molecules of the superacid solution (SbF_6^- and HF). Hydrogen bond/salt bridge interactions are represented as black dashed lines

▪ Classical MD simulation results for the 2-deoxyarabinofuranosyl cation

Figure S10. Averaged occupation of SbF_6^- molecules along the classical MD simulation shown as transparent gray surfaces. One SbF_6^- molecule is represented using stick models for clarity. **(a)** Side and bottom views (3E conformation). **(b)** Side and bottom views (E_3 conformation).

Figure S11. Radial pair distribution functions for the anomeric carbon and the oxygens of protonated hydroxyls of 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation with the solvent molecules, HF (blue line), H₂F⁺ (green line) and SbF₆⁻ (red line).

Figure S12. Interactions present in superacid media (SbF₆⁻ and HF molecules) with the glycosyl cation. Representative hydrogen bond/salt bridges interactions are represented as black dashed lines. **(a)** ³E conformation. **(b)** E₃ conformation.

■ QM/MM MD simulation results for the three glycosyl cations

Figure S13. Hydroxymethyl orientations along the QM/MM metadynamics simulations. **(a)** 2-deoxyglucosyl cation in E₄ conformation. **(b)** 2-deoxygalactosyl cation in ⁴E conformation. **(c)** 2-deoxyarabinofuranosyl cation in ³E conformation.

XIII. Modelling glycosyl cations in enzymatic media

- 2-deoxyglucosyl cation

Figure S14. (a) Conformational FEL of 2-deoxy-D-glucosyl cation on the active site of ScGas2, energy values are given in kcal·mol⁻¹ and each contour line corresponds to 1 kcal·mol⁻¹. (b) Substrate-enzyme interactions in the active site of ScGas2. The 2-deoxy-D-glucosyl cation placed in the -1 subsite displays a hydrogen bond (black dashed line) and a stacking interaction with Tyr307. The sugar placed in -2 subsite has also a stacking interaction with Tyr107. To change the sugar ring conformation towards the E₄ region, C3 and C4 should move up and down, respectively. This would disrupt important interactions that stabilize the sugar chain in the active site, which is energetically unfavourable.

Figure S16. (a) Free energy landscape of the first step of the hydrolysis reaction. The dashed white line corresponds to the lowest free energy path, computed using MEPSAnd [35]. (b) Conformational catalytic itinerary projected onto the conformational free energy profile of an isolated α -L-arabinofuranose.

Table S2. Structural and electronic parameters of relevant points along the reaction pathway. The TS structure was determined by committer analysis [34].

	MC	TS	GEI
C1 – glycosidic O (Å)	1.53 ± 0.09	3.29	3.8 ± 0.09
C1 – Glu ₂₂₁ (Å)	3.94 ± 0.08	2.92	1.47 ± 0.08
O _{Asp297} – H _{Asp297} (Å)	1.02 ± 0.03	0.98	1.05 ± 0.04
H _{Asp297} – glycosidic O (Å)	3.29 ± 0.14	3.09	1.98 ± 0.65
C1 – ring O (Å)	1.40 ± 0.04	1.29	1.41 ± 0.04
C1 (RESP charge)	0.52 ± 0.06	0.36	0.92 ± 0.13
O4 (RESP charge)	-0.66 ± 0.04	-0.26	-0.68 ± 0.12
Φ (°)	244 ± 11	206.4	184 ± 7

The reaction mechanism of *AkAbfB* α -L-arabinofuranosidase corresponds to a dissociative mechanism, in which the glycosidic bond breaks before the nucleophile approaches the anomeric carbon (see Table S2, C1-O1' is 3.29Å and C1- O_{Glu221} is 2.92Å at the TS). The p-nitrophenyl group does not need proton transfer from the acid/base catalytic residue. The conformation of the arabinofuranose ring of the PNP-Araf substrate in the MC changes very little compared to the crystal structure. The conformation evolves from ⁴E conformation in the crystal structure to a conformation in-between ⁴E and ⁴T₀ in the

computed structure (see Figure S15). This slight difference can probably be attributed to the Glu221Gln mutation of the crystal structure. As a result, the mutation does not change substantially the conformation of the substrate at the MC. This is in contrast with most GH complexes with pyranose-type substrates, in which mutation of the nucleophile, a negatively charged residue that strongly interacts with the sugar hydroxyl residues, changes the sugar conformation significantly [36]. As in pyranose-acting GHs, the reaction of *AkAbfB* α -L-arabinofuranosidase goes through a TS with significant oxocarbenium ion-like character, in which the sugar adopts a E_3 conformation. The reaction leads to the formation of the GEI intermediate, in which the arabinofuranose ring adopts a 2T_3 conformation. Therefore, the conformational catalytic itinerary of *AkAbfB* α -L-arabinofuranosidase can be described as ${}^4E / {}^4T_0 \rightarrow [E_3]^\ddagger \rightarrow {}^2T_3$.

Figure S17. Representative structures along the catalytic itinerary of *AkAbfB* α -L-arabinofuranosidase.

■ 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation

Figure S18. (a) Conformational FEL of the 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation in the active site of *AkAbfB*. Energy values are given in kcal·mol⁻¹ and each contour line corresponds to 1 kcal·mol⁻¹. (b) Substrate-enzyme interactions in the active site of *AkAbfB* (sugar in 3E conformation). (c) Substrate-enzyme interactions in the active site of *AkAbfB* (sugar in E_3 conformation). Hydrogen bond interactions are shown as black dashed lines.

XIV. Comparison between superacid and enzymatic media

▪ 2-deoxyglucosyl cation

Figure S19. Intramolecular properties of the 2-deoxyglucosyl cation (⁴E conformation) in gas-phase, superacid and enzymatic environments. From top to bottom: C1-O5 bond distance (blue), C2-C1-O5-C5 dihedral angle (Ω), which reflects the ring planarity (green) and anomeric charge (sum of C1, H1 and O5 charges) (red).

▪ 2-deoxygalactosyl cation

Figure S20. Intramolecular properties of the 2-deoxygalactosyl cation (⁴H₃ conformation) in gas-phase, superacid and enzymatic environments. From top to bottom: C1-O5 bond distance (blue), C2-C1-O5-C5 dihedral angle (Ω), which reflects the ring planarity (green) and anomeric charge (sum of C1, H1 and O5 charges) (red).

2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation

Figure S21. Intramolecular properties of the 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation (E_3 conformation) in gas-phase, superacid and enzymatic environments. From top to bottom: C1-O5 bond distance (blue), C2-C1-O5-C5 dihedral angle (Ω), which reflects the ring planarity (green) and anomeric charge (sum of C1, H1 and O5 charges) (red).

Figure S22 Intramolecular properties of the 2-deoxy-L-arabinofuranosyl cation (3E_3 conformation) in gas-phase, superacid and enzymatic environments. From top to bottom: C1-O5 bond distance (blue), C2-C1-O5-C5 dihedral angle (Ω), which reflects the ring planarity (green) and anomeric charge (sum of C1, H1 and O5 charges) (red).

▪ Glycosyl cation distances and anomeric charge values

Table S3. Glycosyl cation properties in gas-phase

	Conf.	C1-O5 distance (Å)	C2-C1-O5-C5 dih (degrees)	Anomeric charge
Galactosyl	⁴ H ₃	1.267	4	0.37
Furanosyl	E ₃	1.31	-0.6	0.13
Furanosyl	³ E	1.27	-1	0.16
Glucosyl	⁴ E	1.27	1.75	0.29

Table S4. Glycosyl cation properties in superacid media

	Conf.	C1-O5 distance (Å)	C2-C1-O5-C5 dih (degrees)	Anomeric charge	O-H ₂ ⁺ ... F-H distance (Å)	O-H ₂ ⁺ ... F ₆ ⁻ Sb distance (Å)	C1 ... F ₆ ⁻ Sb distance (Å)
Galactosyl	⁴ H ₃	1.27	3	0.74	1.6	1.7	3.1
Furanosyl	E ₃	1.27	-0.5	0.26	1.6	1.7	3.1
Furanosyl	³ E	1.27	-1.5	0.24	1.6	1.7	3.1
Glucosyl	⁴ E	1.27	-2	0.57	1.6	1.7	3.1

Table S5. Glycosyl cation properties in enzyme

	Conf.	C1-O5 distance (Å)	C2-C1-O5-C5 dih (degrees)	Anomeric charge	Hydroxyls – Enzyme residues distance (Å)	C1-Nu distance (Å)
Galactosyl	⁴ H ₃	1.28	-0.2	0.47	1.6-1.9	2.8
Furanosyl	E ₃	1.27	1.43	0.22	1.6	2.8
Furanosyl	³ E	1.27	-1.6	0.19	1.6	4.1
Glucosyl	⁴ E	1.27	0.52	0.40	1.7-1.8	2.9

XV. Gas-phase conformational FELs results

Figure S24. 2-deoxyglucosyl cation in gas-phase. a) Conformational FEL. The 3E conformation is more stable than 4H_3 by $8 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. b) Representative structures of the two main conformations in all the observed hydroxymethyl orientations.

Figure S25. 2-deoxyfuranosyl cation in gas-phase. Conformational FEL. The E_3 conformation is more stable than 3E by $6 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.

XVI. References

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